

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND MODERN METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

Innovative phenomena cause the transition from the knowledge paradigm of the pedagogical process to the individual, from the "communicators" - to the interactive methods of teaching. All of the above, as well as the need to find ways to intensify the use of innovative teaching methods in the teaching of English at school in the context of the ever changing realities of modern society and its active development, determine the urgency of the work and determine the choice of its' topic. The problem of teaching foreign languages in school today certainly requires a systematic analysis of speech-activity from psycholinguistic, linguistic and psychological positions. Traditional methods of teaching a foreign language involve the assimilation of knowledge in artificial situations, so that a future graduate does not see the connection of the subject under study with his future professional activity.

The most effective means of developing the thinking of future graduates is simulation modeling. Such an approach in training provides an imitation of elements of professional activity, its typical and essential features. Its use in foreign language classes makes it possible to form skills and communication skills; develops the habit of self-control, contributes to the real preparation of schoolchildren for forthcoming activities and life in society as a whole; helps to make foreign language lessons more lively, interesting, meaningful, give the opportunity for schoolchildren to express their own opinions more often, express feelings, thoughts, assessments, to think in a foreign language.

The following can be used as methods to improve the professional orientation of studying a foreign language: communication - dialogue about professional information read in a foreign language, analysis of social and professional situations, fulfillment of creative assignments with profile content by schoolchildren, game situations, role plays, quizzes. The practice of applying innovative technologies to improve the professional orientation of learning a foreign language at school, as practice shows, is most noticeable when they are applied in the system of studies, providing mastering a whole complex of skills, laying the effective basis for its

effective profiling in life. Innovative methods of teaching a foreign language aimed at more effective development of the individual and adaptation (both social and professional) within the framework of today's rapidly changing society.

Multilateral method. The modern multilateral method originates from the so-called "Cleveland Plan", developed in 1920. Its main principles are:

-Foreign language can not be learned through mechanical memorization, because is created individually by everyone. Thus, training exercises should be minimized in favor of the spontaneous speech of trainees.

-Language is culture, i.e. cultural knowledge is transferred in the process of teaching the language through authentic language materials.

-Each lesson should be structured around a single focus, trained in one lesson should recognize one isolated unit of study content.

-Grammar, like a dictionary, is taught by measured portions in a strict logical sequence: each subsequent lesson should increase the already available stock.

All four types of speech activity should be present simultaneously in the learning process. The training material is presented by long dialogues with subsequent exercises in the question-answer form. As a rule, the texts offered for studying this method give a good idea of the culture of the country of the studied language. However, the role of the teacher limits the possibility of creative use of the learned material by trainees in situations of direct communication with each other.

The method of complete physical reaction. This method is based on two basic assumptions. First, on the fact that the skills of perception of foreign oral speech must precede the development of all other skills, as happens in young children.

Secondly, the language of the lesson is usually limited to concepts that describe the situation "here and now" and are easily explained by examples in the studied language. Trainees should never be forced to speak until they themselves feel that they are ready for it. The method is not intended for teaching reading and writing, and also the language, to the extent that it is learned in teaching this method, is not a natural language of everyday communication.

The natural method. The goal of the training is to achieve an intermediate level of knowledge of a foreign language among students. The teacher never pays attention to errors in speech, as it is believed that this can slow the development of speech skills. The early productive period begins with the moment when the passive vocabulary of students reaches about 500 vocabulary units. From the point of view of pedagogy, the main components of the innovative approach to learning are the activity approach. This approach is based on the idea that the functioning and development of the personality, as well as the interpersonal relations of the students, are mediated by the goals, content and tasks of socially significant activity.

Teaching a foreign language using the Internet. The introduction of information and communication technologies in the learning process began not so long ago. However, the pace of its spread is incredibly rapid. The use of Internet technologies in classes in a foreign language is an effective factor for the development of motivation of trainees. Since classes take place in an informal setting, students are given freedom of action, and some of them can "flash" their knowledge in the field of ICT. The prospects for using Internet technologies today are quite wide. It can be:

Correspondence with residents of English-speaking countries via e-mail. Participation in international Internet conferences, seminars and other network projects of this kind;

In addition, it is possible to exchange presentations between teachers from different countries. As the pedagogical experience shows, the work on creation of Internet resources is of interest to students with their novelty, relevance, and creativity. The organization of the cognitive activity of pupils in small groups makes it possible to show their activity to each child. However, it should be noted that information technology, Internet technologies - this is by no means a panacea for increasing the motivation and independence of students in the process of learning a foreign language in the cognitive process. To achieve maximum effect, it is necessary to use a wide range of innovative, including, of course, various media education technologies in the learning process.

Language portfolio as one of the most promising means of teaching a foreign language at school. The language portfolio in modern conditions is defined as a package of working materials that represent one or another experience / result of the learner's learning activity in mastering a foreign language. Such a package / set of materials gives an opportunity for the student and teacher on the result of the training activities presented in the language portfolio, to analyze and evaluate the scope of the educational work and the range of the student's achievements in the field of language learning and foreign culture. For the first time, the idea of creating a self-assessment tool for owning a foreign language appeared in Switzerland more than 10 years ago.

At present, the Council of Europe has established the Accreditation Committee, where the projects of language portfolios are being sent, which are further evaluated and discussed, as well as accreditation. The objectives and forms of work with the language portfolio can be different. In terms of its conceptual essence, the language portfolio is a flexible educational tool that can be adapted to almost any learning situation.

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